

Atlantic Ecosystems Assessment, Forecasting & Sustainability

Deliverable number D5.4 Report on results of all experiments performed

Dissemination level: Public

Related Work Package	WP5 - Advances in System Ecology
Related task(s)	Task 5.4
Lead beneficiary	Stellenbosch University (SUN)
Author(s)	T. Makhalanyane (SUN)
Due date	30.11.2024
Submission date	28.02.2026
Type	Report
Status and version	Final submitted version

Declaration: Any work or result described therein is a genuine output of the AtlantECO project. Any other source will be properly referenced where and when relevant.

Table of Contents

1 Version History	3
2 Executive summary	4
3 Introduction	5
4 Background and methodology	7
Extended Incubations and Depth-Resolved Sampling	8
DNA Extraction and 16S rRNA Gene Sequencing	9
Trace Metal Analysis	9
Depth related differences in community composition	9
Network analysis of microbial communities and responses to nutrient amendments	10
Taxa responses to nutrient amendments in an epipelagic and mesopelagic region	11
Trace metal correlation analysis of taxa in an epipelagic and mesopelagic region	14
Additional Context	15
5 Conclusions	16
Depth-Related Differences in Community Responses	16
Network Reorganisation and Community Resilience	16
Taxon-Specific Responses and Biogeochemical Implications	16
Trace Metal–Taxa Associations	17
Implications for Southern Ocean Biogeochemistry	18
Contribution to AtlantECO WP5: Advances in System Ecology	18
Strengthening Predictive Understanding of Carbon Cycling	18
Advancing Network-Based System Ecology	18
Addressing Knowledge Gaps in Understudied Regions and Seasons	19
Implications for Climate-Relevant Nutrient Perturbations	19
6 References	20

1 Version History

Version	Authors	Summary of changes	Date
1	Thulani Makhalanyane	final version	28.02.2026

2 Executive summary

This deliverable reports the results of experimental analyses focused on elucidating microbial communities and their responses to nutrient co-limitation under WP5 (Task 5.4). We contribute towards advancements in microbial ecology, under the auspices of the AtlantECO project, and substantially advance knowledge regarding microbiota in underexplored systems. Through a combination of dedicated research cruises, including voyages on the RV SA Agulhas II and the Schooner Tara Oceans, we combine trace metal limitation experiments, genome scale metabolic analyses, and bioinformatic analyses to explore bacterial, archaeal and viral communities in these regions. The WP has contributed towards substantial advances to understanding structure, function and environmental vulnerability in underexplored regions, influenced by large rivers, off the coast of Africa.

Field-based experimental work conducted in the Southern Ocean, and samples were collected just north of the important Benguela upwelling system. We measured nutrient, trace metals, and iron limitation and co-limitation dynamics using replicated mesocosms. Our work provides insights regarding underexplored deep regions of the ocean, and particularly microbial contributions to biogeochemistry.

This document is based on the terms and conditions established in the Grant Agreement (GA) and its Annexes, as well as in the Consortium Agreement (CA).

3 Introduction

Understanding the effects of environmental variables on microbiomes remains a major ecological endeavour. Previous studies have shown that the oceans harbour substantial levels of phylogenetic and functional diversity 1-3, despite the depauperate and nutrient limited conditions in some regions. While we lack insights regarding taxonomic and functional diversity in large regions of the ocean, with estimates suggesting that less than 20% of marine surfaces have been explored, there is considerable depth regarding the structure and function of environmental microbiomes. However, the precise mechanisms and environmental drivers remain unclear.

Students trained and synergies

This work package leveraged the support firstly from the University of Pretoria (as the WP leader and then later Stellenbosch University).

- Dr. C.D. Dithugoe
- Dr. O Makinde
- Dr. Diego Castillo
- Dr. Mayibongwe Buthelezi
- Ms. Mancha Mabaso
- Ms. Caitlyn Fourie
- Ms. Elizabe Malan

Key outputs include contributions to:

1. Sarmiento, Hugo, Paula Huber, Célio Dias Santos-Júnior, André Abreu, Thulani P. Makhalanyane, Natasha Karenyi, and Emma Rocke. "The southern gap in ocean microbiome science." *Ocean Microbiology* 1, no. 1 (2025): 6.
2. Makhalanyane, T., Bezuidt, O.K., Castillo, D., du Plessis, T., Palmer, M. and Hugenholtz, P., 2025. Endemic dark ocean microbiomes drive carbon cycling in the Southern Ocean. Under revision *Nature Communications*
3. Buthelezi, Z.M., Pierneef, R.E., Bezuidt, O.K.I. and Makhalanyane, T.P., 2025. High-quality metagenomic-assembled genomes from sea ice and seawater of the Southern Ocean. *Microbiology Resource Announcements*, 14(7), pp.e01298-24.
4. Wang, F., Hinrichs, K.U., Takai, K., Makhalanyane, T., Hatha Abdulla, M. and Jebbar, M., 2025, April. Global Subseafloor Ecosystem and Sustainability (GSES). In *EGU General Assembly Conference Abstracts* (pp. EGU25-4175).
5. Makhalanyane, T., 2025. *Disentangling the drivers of bacterial and viral communities in the Southern Ocean* (No. OOS2025-315). Copernicus Meetings.
6. Buthelezi, M. and Makhalanyane, T.P., 2024, December. The significant role of the Southern Ocean microbes in the cycling of dimethylsulfoniopropionate. In *AGU Fall Meeting Abstracts*(Vol. 2024, pp. OS22A-08).
7. Thompson, C., Ortmann, A.C., Makhalanyane, T. and Thompson, F., 2024. Leveraging marine biotechnology for an All-Atlantic sustainable blue economy. *Trends in Biotechnology*, 42(8), pp.939-941.
8. Thompson, C., Ortmann, A.C., Bolhuis, H., Makhalanyane, T. and Thompson, F., 2024. Harnessing marine microbiomes to develop a sustainable, all-Atlantic bioeconomy. *Mlife*, 3(2), p.163.
9. Makhalanyane, T.P., Bezuidt, O.K., Pierneef, R.E., Mizrachi, E., Zeze, A., Fossou, R.K., Kouadjo, C.G., Duodu, S., Chikere, C.B., Babalola, O.O. and Klein, A., 2023. African microbiomes matter. *Nature Reviews Microbiology*, 21(8), pp.479-481.

10. Dithugoe, C.D., Bezuidt, O.K., Cavan, E.L., Froneman, W.P., Thomalla, S.J. and Makhalanyane, T.P., 2023. Bacteria and archaea regulate particulate organic matter export in suspended and sinking marine particle fractions. *Mosphere*, 8(3), pp.e00420-22.
11. Akpudo, Y.M., Bezuidt, O.K. and Makhalanyane, T.P., 2023. Metagenome-assembled genomes of four Southern Ocean Archaea harbor multiple genes linked to polyethylene terephthalate and polyhydroxybutyrate plastic degradation. *Microbiology Resource Announcements*, 12(3), pp.e01098-22
12. Castillo, D.J., Dithugoe, C.D., Bezuidt, O.K. and Makhalanyane, T.P., 2022. Microbial ecology of the Southern Ocean. *FEMS Microbiology Ecology*, 98(11), p.fiac123.
13. Dithugoe, C.D., Bezuidt, O., Cavan, E., Froneman, W., Thomalla, S. and Makhalanyane, T.P., 2022, March. Disentangling the role of prokaryotes in regulating export flux via suspended and sinking organic matter in the Southern Ocean. In *2022 Goldschmidt Conference*. GOLDSCHMIDT
14. Castillo, D.J., Dithugoe, C.D., Bezuidt, O.K. and Makhalanyane, T.P., 2022. Microbial ecology of the Southern Ocean. *FEMS Microbiology Ecology*, 98(11), p.fiac123.

4 Background and methodology

4.1 Background

The Southern Ocean (SO) is a critical component of the Earth system, exerting a disproportionate influence on global climate regulation. Although it covers approximately 20% of the Earth's surface, it accounts for ~40% of global oceanic CO₂ uptake and ~75% of heat uptake associated with atmospheric CO₂ increases (Frölicher et al., 2015; Rintoul, 2018). This strong carbon and heat sequestration capacity is tightly linked to marine microbial processes that drive primary productivity during the austral summer and nutrient replenishment during the austral winter.

Large areas of the SO are characterised as High-Nutrient, Low-Chlorophyll (HNLC) systems. Despite elevated concentrations of macronutrients (e.g., nitrate and phosphate), primary productivity is constrained by low availability of essential micronutrients, particularly iron and manganese (Moore et al., 2013). While trace metal limitation has been extensively studied in surface waters—primarily focusing on phytoplankton productivity during the austral summer—comparatively little attention has been given to microbial communities in the mesopelagic (“twilight”) zone, especially during austral winter.

Prokaryotic communities in the mesopelagic zone are responsible for approximately 70% of oceanic carbon remineralisation (Giering et al., 2014). Emerging evidence suggests that trace metals may also limit microbial metabolism in these deeper waters (Li et al., 2024). Iron and manganese serve as essential cofactors in key metabolic pathways, including photosynthetic systems and respiratory processes, and can act as alternative electron acceptors under low-oxygen conditions, thereby supporting heterotrophic metabolism and carbon oxidation (Lovley & Phillips, 1988; Hyun et al., 2017).

Microbial responses to altered nutrient flux are known to be environment-specific (Bergo et al., 2022), yet there remains limited understanding of how trace metal availability shapes microbial community structure, metabolic potential, and ecological organisation in the Southern Ocean mesopelagic zone. This knowledge gap is particularly significant given that carbon remineralisation rates in the SO twilight zone are lower than in other ocean basins, enhancing its effectiveness as a long-term carbon sink.

4.2 Methodology

To address this knowledge gap, we conducted trace metal supplementation experiments using seawater collected from subantarctic waters during the SCALE22 cruise. The primary objective was to determine how increased availability of iron and manganese influences microbial community composition, diversity, and ecological network structure in both epipelagic and mesopelagic communities.

We hypothesised that increased iron and manganese availability would induce measurable shifts in mesopelagic microbial communities comparable in magnitude to those observed in epipelagic systems. To test this, controlled mesocosm experiments were established using water collected from both depth strata. Iron and manganese were supplemented individually and in combination to simulate altered micronutrient flux conditions.

This experimental framework allowed us to directly evaluate trace metal limitation effects across vertical gradients and to assess implications for carbon remineralisation, microbial network organisation, and nutrient cycling processes in the Southern Ocean.

Two 48-hour incubation experiments were conducted during the SCALE22 cruise in the polar upwelling zone (~54°S) and within the Marginal Ice Zone (MIZ) at station OD2. Seawater was collected from the upper mixed layer (~50 m) using a GEOTRACES-compliant CTD rosette equipped with trace-metal-clean GoFlo bottles.

Upon retrieval, bottles were transferred into a trace metal clean container, rinsed externally with ultrapure Milli-Q water, and inverted three times to ensure sample homogenisation. Seawater was passed through a 200 µm mesh to remove grazers prior to incubation.

Water was dispensed into 250 mL acid-washed polycarbonate (PC) bottles after triple rinsing with sample water. Four treatments were established in triplicate:

- Control (no amendment)
- +Fe
- +Mn
- +Fe + Mn

Iron and manganese spike solutions were prepared in 0.01 mol L⁻¹ ultrapure hydrochloric acid. These treatments were designed to assess potential Fe and Mn co-limitation of Southern Ocean phytoplankton and microbial communities during winter conditions.

Initial condition samples were collected for:

- Dissolved trace metals (Fe and Mn)
- Flow cytometry
- Macronutrients
- Chlorophyll-a
- Photophysiology

Incubations were conducted in customized Minus40 Specialized Refrigeration™ units (MINUS40, South Africa) equipped with programmable LED lighting and temperature control. Bottles were placed in clear polyethylene bags to minimise contamination risk and incubated at in situ temperature under the lowest achievable light levels, following the natural day–night cycle.

Extended Incubations and Depth-Resolved Sampling

A total of 24 additional seawater samples were collected at station OD2 (58.38472° S, 0.49965° W) from 50 m (epipelagic) and 500 m (mesopelagic) depths using trace-metal-clean GoFlo bottles.

Samples were amended with:

- FeCl₃ (2 nM final concentration)
- MnCl₂ (4 nM final concentration)
- Combined FeCl₃ + MnCl₂

Incubations were conducted in 10 L acid-washed carboys over 1-, 5-, and 7-day periods at 4°C under controlled light exposure.

At each time point, samples were filtered using a dual filtration system onto 0.22 µm filters mounted on 142 mm Isopore membrane filters (Merck, USA) to target bacterioplankton communities (following Pesant et al., 2015). Filters were flash-frozen in liquid nitrogen and stored at -80°C until laboratory processing.

DNA Extraction and 16S rRNA Gene Sequencing

DNA was extracted from filters using the DNeasy PowerWater Kit according to the manufacturer's protocol.

The V4 region of the 16S rRNA gene was amplified using modified primers:

- 515F: GTGYCAGCMGCCGCGGTAA
- 806R: GGACTACNVGGGTWTCTAA

Library preparation and sequencing were performed on an Illumina NovaSeq platform (CD Genomics). Raw demultiplexed reads were processed using the DADA2 workflow (v1.26) following Callahan et al. (2016). Taxonomic assignment was performed against the SILVA 138.1 database. Mitochondrial, chloroplast-derived sequences and singletons were removed prior to downstream analyses

Trace Metal Analysis

Dissolved trace metals were analysed at the TracEx Laboratory, Stellenbosch University, following the method described by Samanta et al. (2021). Samples were processed using an online SC-4 DX seaFAST S3 (ESI® seaFAST) preconcentration system coupled to an Agilent® 7900 quadrupole ICP-MS.

Analytical accuracy was verified using:

- NASS-7 certified reference material
- GEOTRACES GSC-19 and GSP reference materials
- In-house reference seawater

Measured values fell within acceptable recovery ranges. Method blanks were determined using 2% ultrapure HCl, and limits of detection (LOD) were calculated as three times the standard deviation of preconcentrated blanks (n = 7).

4.3 Results

Depth related differences in community composition

Few studies have investigated microbial community responses to nutrient amendments in the SO. Here, we show that microbial communities, recovered from deep zones of the ocean, appear to have different responses compared with those from shallow zones. While nutrient amendments did not result in significant differences in the composition of taxa retrieved from each depth (epipelagic and mesopelagic), the sample dissimilarity within each group was significantly greater in the deep region compared to the shallow region (Figure 1). However, increases in unique ASV counts as a consequence of nutrient amendments were observed to be greater in the epipelagic region compared to the mesopelagic for both Fe and Fe+Mn experiments (S1). While each nutrient amendment did not elicit any overall significant differences in microbial community composition for either depth (Figure 1a), the very different clustering patterns exhibited by each community indicated that they had asymmetrical responses to these nutrient amendments and thus may have different stress tolerances for brief nutrient pulse disturbances (Dinasquet et al., 2018; Sheyn et al., 2025).

Figure 1 Sample sites of the SCALE22 cruise aboard the S.A Agulhas 2. Sampling for current study indicated in red.

Network analysis of microbial communities and responses to nutrient amendments

Co-occurrence networks were used to investigate microbial responses to trace metal supplementation. Our data shows a uniform response to nutrient amendments with regards to negative and positive associations between taxa within each community. However, the mesopelagic communities responded with a significant increase in community modularity in both Fe+Mn and Fe experiments whereas these nutrient amendments elicited a minimal response in the epipelagic communities (Figure 2). It is generally assumed that increases to modularity reflect increases in community resilience as well as environmental variability (Parter, Kashtan and Alon, 2007; D’Alelio *et al.*, 2019; Hernandez *et al.*, 2021), and this may make sense in the context of microbial communities having greater access to essential micronutrients such as trace metals. Previous studies on nutrient amendment and network reassembly are rare in the marine context and have shown conflicting observations to changes in modularity and negative:positive (Chen *et al.*, 2022; Dai *et al.*, 2022) and so further investigations will need to be done to establish consensus.

Figure 2 Principal Coordinate Analysis (PCoA) plot based on Bray–Curtis dissimilarity of microbial community composition in mesocosm samples. Samples are grouped according to nutrient amendments (control, iron, manganese, and iron+manganese treatments) and depth (shallow 50 m; deep 500 m).

Taxa responses to nutrient amendments in an epipelagic and mesopelagic region

Nutrient amendments elicited different abundance transformations for specific orders and families in shallow and deep region to a greater degree in the latter overall (Figure 3). *Cryomorpaceae*, *Sphingomonadaceae*, *Rhodobacteraceae*, and *Nitrosomonadaceae* all had significantly greater positive responses to all nutrient amendments in the mesopelagic region compared to the epipelagic region. In the literature, these taxa have been implicated in various biogeochemical processes critical in marine ecosystems. *Cryomorpaceae* has associations to marine alga like *Phaeocystis antarctica* and *Tetraselmis suecica* (Hernandez-Magana *et al.*, 2021; Roager *et al.*, 2024), it has been found in the SO (Delmont *et al.*, 2015; Hernandez-Magana *et al.*, 2021) and implicated in carbon, nitrogen, sulphur and iron metabolism (Delmont *et al.*, 2015; Brown *et al.*, 2022b). *Sphingomonadaceae* has been found at various depths including pelagic regions (He, Baltar and Wang, 2025; Li *et al.*, 2024) and may have mechanisms for plastic bioremediation (Oh and Choi, 2019). *Rhodobacteraceae* found to have Fe^{3+} acquisition genes in Southern Ocean environments and implicated in trace metal cycling of a number of elements such as manganese, zinc and nickel (R. Zhang *et al.*, 2023; Kong *et al.*, 2024). They are critical for diatom biogeochemical cycling and may be involved in the remineralisation of carbon in the mesopelagic region (Baumas *et al.*, 2021; Isaac, Mohamed and Amin, 2024). This response indicates potential coupling between trace metal availability and microbial carbon turnover in mesopelagic regions with implications for biogeochemical fluxes and carbon sequestration capabilities impacted by anthropogenically related trace nutrient fluxes. *Nitrosomonadaceae* has been found in Antarctica marine environments (Garber *et al.*, 2021; Alcamán-Arias *et al.*, 2022; Howland *et al.*, 2025) and is primarily responsible for a number of denitrification reactions that are coupled with iron and manganese ions (Tian *et al.*, 2020; D. Zhang *et al.*, 2023; Zhang *et al.*, 2024). These iron dependent denitrification bacteria are being investigated for potential

bioremediation technologies (Tian *et al.*, 2020). Some taxa such as *Arenicellaceae* and *Alcanivoracaceae* had inverse responses to Fe and Mn amendments within the mesopelagic region while other taxa such as *Actinomarinaceae* and *Caulobacteraceae* had reduced abundances to Fe and Mn respectively. Interestingly, *Moraxellaceae* was the only family taxa found to be more abundant in the epipelagic region under Fe+Mn amendment and not so within the mesopelagic region. This taxa has been found in a number of SO environments (Toro *et al.*, 2021; Ozturk, Feyzioglu and Altinok, 2022) and has some association with plastic degradation enzymes that are iron and manganese dependent (Dodhia *et al.*, 2023).

Figure 3 Microbial Network responses to nutrient amendments in the different regions for modularity and ratio of negative and positive cohesions.

Using differential abundance analysis, a variety of taxa were more differentially abundant in the deep zone with the most taxa represented in the Fe+Mn, then the Mn, and the least amount in the Fe amendment while no differentially abundant taxa were found in the shallow region (Figure 4). *Asciadiaceihabitans* was found to be more differentially abundant in all three nutrient amendments. This taxa has been implicated in both nitrogen metabolism (Weigel *et al.*, 2022) and heterotrophic dissolved organic matter (DOM) utilisation (Eigemann *et al.*, 2023; Piontek *et al.*, 2024). Out of the seven differentially abundant taxa in the Fe+Mn experiment, *Pseudonocardia* was the most so (Figure 4). Members from this taxa have been implicated in pollutant biodegradation (Vainberg *et al.*, 2006; Ma *et al.*, 2021; Boondaeng *et al.*, 2025) and have been found in metal rich environments with potentially novel biotherapeutic natural products (Munir Ahamed *et al.*, 2025) which may be trace metal dependent (Zhang *et al.*, 2022; Mular *et al.*, 2024).

Figure 4 Log transformation bacterial order (a) and family (b) taxa in each nutrient amendment. Taxa were filtered to those that had a greater expression of change of $-1/1$

Trace metal correlation analysis of taxa in an epipelagic and mesopelagic region

Most of the significant correlations with trace metals were found in the deep zone with positive associations found with zinc and negative associations found with cadmium, cobalt (Co), copper (Cu) and Nickel (Ni) (Figure 5). *Methylobacterium* which had negative correlations with Cd, Co, Cu, and Ni, are able to utilise methylated aromatic compounds and even degrade polyesters such as plastics (Lee, Stolyar and Marx, 2022; Lee *et al.*, 2024). Aromatic compounds like humic substances are able to sequester trace metals more readily (Baken *et al.*, 2011; Nakayama *et al.*, 2025).

The mesopelagic region cannot rely on photoautotrophy but sustains its energetic requirements by the combination of heterotrophic, chemoautotrophic and chemo mixotrophic processes together with physicochemical processes (Giering *et al.*, 2014). Significant gaps remain in our understanding of Southern Ocean biogeochemical processes during the Austral winter despite its known importance for global Earth system stability (Newman *et al.*, 2019). For example, these observations may not just be limited to micronutrients such as trace metals but could also apply to macronutrients such as phosphorus and nitrogen containing compounds (Larsen, Wilhelm and Lennon, 2019; Dai *et al.*, 2022). How these microbes reassemble themselves during nutrient perturbation events is important for community resilience and their interactions with phytoplankton (Zhang *et al.*, 2020; Qiao *et al.*, 2025), and currently there is limited mechanistic understanding of these events (Gralka *et al.*, 2020). Much of this is due to technical and logistical limitations but as technologies and autonomous sampling improves, we envision that data collection, and observational networks will expand into previously hard to reach locations (Boyd *et al.*, 2024).

Figure 5 Differential abundance analysis of microbial taxa using DESeq2, showing comparisons between control and nutrient-amended mesocosms

Additional Context

Bowler was onboard Tara in Antarctica with Al Tagliabue from Liverpool, setting up trace metal sampling in the context of an iron gradient in Weddell Sea and nutrient gradients around a large tabular iceberg.

Bowler helped Makhalanyane to develop studies of nutrient co-limitation to be studied on board Tara in Benguela upwelling region.

Bowler's lab has been instrumental in advancing our understanding of marine plankton ecosystems through a combination of experimental, computational, and theoretical approaches in the following papers that acknowledge AtlantECO funding:

In **Pierella Karlusich et al. (2020)**, Bowler's lab contextualized the evolution of phytoplankton research, emphasizing the transformative impact of omics technologies. By exploring historical and contemporary insights, the lab highlighted how molecular tools unveil phytoplankton's ecological and biogeochemical roles, setting the stage for future integrative studies.

In **Chaffron et al. (2021)**, Bowler's team contributed significantly to mapping the environmental vulnerabilities of the global ocean's epipelagic plankton interactome. This work combined Tara Oceans data with advanced computational modeling to identify critical ecological relationships and stressors, underlining the susceptibility of marine plankton to environmental changes.

Régimbeau et al. (2022) included Bowler's team's expertise in integrating genome-scale metabolic modeling with ecological theory. Their efforts elucidated how metabolic networks shape plankton niches and biodiversity, offering novel insights into the biochemical drivers of ecological interactions in the ocean.

In **Tara Ocean Foundation et al. (2022)**, Bowler helped define research priorities for the ocean microbiome, advocating for multidisciplinary approaches that integrate microbiology, ecology, and oceanography to address pressing challenges in marine science. Bowler is corresponding author on the paper.

The study by **Rigonato et al. (2023)** drew on Bowler's lab's expertise to compare mesopelagic planktonic communities across oceanic regions. Their contributions to the Tara Oceans initiative facilitated an unprecedented understanding of biodiversity and functional traits in this crucial but understudied zone.

In **Giordano et al. (2024)**, Bowler's group contributed to developing genome-scale community models that revealed conserved metabolic cross-feedings within epipelagic bacterioplankton. These findings underscored the interconnectedness of marine microbial communities and their metabolic dependencies.

Finally, in **El Hourany et al. (2024)**, Bowler's lab bridged satellite remote sensing and molecular biology using machine learning techniques to estimate phytoplankton community structures from space. This innovative approach has far-reaching implications for monitoring ocean health and understanding phytoplankton dynamics at global scales.

5 Conclusions

Depth-Related Differences in Community Responses

This study provides new insight into microbial responses to trace metal amendments in the Southern Ocean (SO), particularly within under-studied mesopelagic environments. While nutrient amendments (Fe, Mn, and Fe+Mn) did not result in statistically significant shifts in overall taxonomic composition at either depth, clear depth-dependent differences in community response were observed.

Mesopelagic communities exhibited significantly greater within-group dissimilarity compared to epipelagic communities, indicating higher compositional variability under nutrient perturbation. In contrast, epipelagic communities showed a greater increase in unique ASV richness following Fe and Fe+Mn amendments. These patterns suggest asymmetrical responses to short-term nutrient pulses, likely reflecting differing ecological strategies, stress tolerances, and metabolic constraints between shallow and deep microbial assemblages.

Overall, the results demonstrate that mesopelagic microbial communities respond differently to trace metal perturbations compared to surface communities, highlighting the importance of depth-resolved assessments in predicting ecosystem responses to changing micronutrient fluxes.

Network Reorganisation and Community Resilience

Co-occurrence network analyses revealed depth-specific restructuring in response to trace metal supplementation. While the balance of positive and negative associations remained relatively stable, mesopelagic communities exhibited a significant increase in network modularity following Fe and Fe+Mn amendments, whereas epipelagic communities showed minimal structural change.

Increased modularity is often associated with enhanced ecological compartmentalisation and potential resilience to environmental perturbation. The observed increase in modularity in the mesopelagic zone may reflect adaptive reorganisation in response to improved micronutrient availability. These findings suggest that trace metal pulses can influence not only taxonomic composition but also the interaction architecture of deep-ocean microbial communities.

Given the limited number of marine studies linking nutrient amendments to network topology, these results contribute valuable empirical evidence toward understanding how microbial interaction networks reorganise under altered trace metal regimes.

Taxon-Specific Responses and Biogeochemical Implications

Trace metal amendments elicited stronger and more diverse taxon-specific responses in the mesopelagic zone than in the epipelagic zone. Several families—including Cryomorphaceae, Sphingomonadaceae, Rhodobacteraceae, and Nitrosomonadaceae—showed significantly greater positive responses in deep waters.

These taxa are implicated in key biogeochemical functions, including:

- Carbon remineralisation and dissolved organic matter degradation
- Nitrogen transformation and denitrification
- Sulphur and trace metal cycling
- Iron acquisition and metal-dependent metabolic pathways

The enrichment of Rhodobacteraceae and Nitrosomonadaceae under Fe and Mn amendments is particularly notable, given their roles in iron acquisition, manganese transformation, and coupled nitrogen cycling. These responses indicate potential mechanistic links between trace metal availability and microbial carbon and nitrogen turnover in the mesopelagic zone.

Differential abundance analysis further showed that nutrient-driven responses were largely restricted to the deep zone, with the strongest effects observed under combined Fe+Mn amendments. Taxa such as Ascidiaceihabitans and Pseudonocardia displayed significant enrichment, suggesting potential roles in heterotrophic DOM utilisation, nitrogen metabolism, and metal-associated biochemical processes.

These findings collectively indicate that trace metal inputs may influence microbial-driven carbon processing and nutrient regeneration in the Southern Ocean twilight zone, with implications for carbon sequestration efficiency.

Trace Metal–Taxa Associations

Correlation analyses revealed that most significant trace metal–taxa relationships occurred in the mesopelagic region. Positive associations were observed with zinc, while negative associations were found with cadmium, cobalt, copper, and nickel.

These relationships highlight the sensitivity of deep-ocean microbial assemblages to trace metal gradients. Several correlated taxa are known to utilise complex organic substrates and may interact with metal-binding organic compounds such as humic substances. Such interactions suggest that trace metals and organic matter composition jointly influence microbial community structure and function in the twilight zone.

Figure 6 Pearson correlation matrix showing associations between statistically significant microbial taxa and trace metal concentrations in the different depths (50 m shallow; 500m deep). Significant differences are marked by asterisk (** $P < 0.001$; ** $P < 0.01$; * $P < 0.05$).

Implications for Southern Ocean Biogeochemistry

The mesopelagic Southern Ocean sustains its energetic demands primarily through heterotrophic, chemoautotrophic, and mixotrophic processes rather than photoautotrophy. Given its relatively low carbon remineralisation rates compared to other ocean basins, the region functions as an effective long-term carbon sink.

Our results demonstrate that trace metal perturbations can restructure mesopelagic microbial communities at both compositional and network levels. These findings underscore the importance of micronutrient availability in regulating microbial carbon cycling and nutrient regeneration processes in the Southern Ocean.

Significant knowledge gaps remain regarding winter biogeochemical dynamics and microbial reassembly following nutrient perturbations. However, advances in trace-metal-clean sampling, molecular ecology, and autonomous ocean observation systems are expected to substantially improve predictive understanding of Southern Ocean ecosystem responses to climate-driven and anthropogenic changes in nutrient flux.

Contribution to AtlantECO WP5: Advances in System Ecology

This study directly contributes to the objectives of WP5 (Advances in System Ecology) by providing experimental evidence of how trace metal availability influences microbial community structure, interaction networks, and potential biogeochemical functioning in the Southern Ocean. By integrating controlled nutrient amendment experiments with high-resolution molecular and network analyses, this work advances system-level understanding of microbial responses to environmental perturbation—one of the core aims of AtlantECO.

The results demonstrate clear depth-dependent differences in microbial responses to Fe and Mn supplementation. While epipelagic communities exhibited increases in unique ASV richness under nutrient amendments, mesopelagic communities showed significantly greater compositional variability and pronounced restructuring of interaction networks. These findings align with AtlantECO's objective to move beyond surface-layer analyses and incorporate vertical ecosystem complexity into predictive ecological models.

Strengthening Predictive Understanding of Carbon Cycling

A central goal of AtlantECO is to improve mechanistic understanding of microbial contributions to carbon flux and ocean biogeochemistry under global change. The observed increase in network modularity in mesopelagic communities following Fe and Fe+Mn amendments suggests functional reorganisation under altered micronutrient regimes. Because modularity is often associated with ecological resilience and niche compartmentalisation, these results provide empirical data relevant to modelling microbial stability under shifting nutrient conditions.

The enrichment of taxa linked to carbon remineralisation, nitrogen transformation, and trace metal cycling (e.g., Rhodobacteraceae, Nitrosomonadaceae, Cryomorphaceae) under trace metal amendments further indicates potential coupling between micronutrient flux and deep-ocean carbon turnover. Given that the Southern Ocean twilight zone plays a disproportionate role in long-term carbon sequestration, these findings provide valuable constraints for ecosystem and Earth system models being developed within AtlantECO.

Advancing Network-Based System Ecology

AtlantECO emphasises integrative, network-based approaches to understanding marine ecosystem functioning. The co-occurrence network analyses presented here demonstrate that trace metal perturbations

influence not only taxonomic composition but also microbial interaction architecture. The depth-specific increase in modularity in mesopelagic networks highlights the importance of considering microbial interaction topology when assessing ecosystem resilience and function.

These findings support AtlantECO's broader effort to integrate omics, ecological theory, and modelling frameworks to move toward predictive system ecology rather than purely descriptive biodiversity assessments.

Addressing Knowledge Gaps in Understudied Regions and Seasons

A key AtlantECO objective is to expand knowledge into underrepresented regions and environmental contexts. This work addresses significant gaps in understanding Southern Ocean winter biogeochemistry and mesopelagic microbial dynamics—areas that remain logistically challenging and poorly characterised.

By generating trace-metal-clean experimental datasets from both epipelagic and mesopelagic waters during winter conditions, this study contributes novel observations that strengthen the geographical and seasonal coverage of AtlantECO outputs.

Implications for Climate-Relevant Nutrient Perturbations

Changes in atmospheric deposition, ocean circulation, and cryospheric processes may alter trace metal fluxes to Southern Ocean ecosystems. The experimental evidence presented here indicates that mesopelagic microbial communities are particularly sensitive to such perturbations, with implications for nutrient regeneration efficiency, carbon remineralisation rates, and long-term sequestration.

These findings provide mechanistic insight relevant to AtlantECO's overarching mission: improving understanding of how marine microbial ecosystems respond to environmental change and how these responses influence global biogeochemical cycles.

6 References

Pierella Karlusich, J. J., Ibarbalz, F. M. and Bowler, C. Exploration of marine phytoplankton: from their historical appreciation to the omics era. **J. Plankton Res.** 42: 595–612 (2020).

Chaffron, S., Delage, E., Budinich, M., Vintache, D., Henry, N., Nef, C., Ardyna, M., Zayed, A. A., Junger, P. C., Galand, P. E., Lovejoy, C., Murray, A. E., Sarmiento, H., *Tara Oceans* coordinators, Acinas, S. G., Babin, M., Iudicone, D., Jaillon, O., Karsenti, E., Wincker, P., Karp-Boss, L., Sullivan, M. B., Bowler, C., de Vargas, C. and Eveillard, D. Environmental vulnerability of the global ocean epipelagic plankton community interactome. **Sci Adv.** 7: eabg1921 (2021).

Régimbeau, A., Budinich, M., Larhlimi, A., Pierella Karlusich, J. J., Aumont, O., Memery, L., Bowler, C. and Eveillard, D. Contribution of genome-scale metabolic modelling to niche theory. **Ecol. Lett.** 25: 1352-1364 (2022).

Tara Ocean Foundation, *Tara Oceans*, European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL), European Marine Biological Resource Centre - European Research Infrastructure Consortium (EMBRIC-ERIC). Priorities for ocean microbiome research. **Nat. Microbiol.** 7: 937-947 (2022).

Rigonato J, Budinich M, Murillo AA, Brandão MC, Pierella Karlusich JJ, Soviadan YD, Gregory AC, Endo H, Kokoszka F, Vik D, Henry N, Frémont P, Labadie K, Zayed AA, Dimier C, Picheral M, Searson S, Poulain J, Kandels S, Pesant S, Karsenti E; *Tara Oceans* coordinators; Bork P, Bowler C, de Vargas C, Eveillard D, Gehlen M, Iudicone D, Lombard F, Ogata H, Stemmann L, Sullivan MB, Sunagawa S, Wincker P, Chaffron S, and Jaillon O. Ocean-wide comparisons of mesopelagic planktonic community structures. **ISME Commun.** 3: 83. (2023). doi: 10.1038/s43705-023-00279-9.

Giordano, N., Gaudin, M., Trottier, C., Delage, E., Nef, C., Bowler, C. and Chaffron, S. Genome-scale community modelling reveals conserved metabolic cross-feedings in epipelagic bacterioplankton communities. **Nat Commun.** 15:2721 (2024).

El Hourany, R., Pierella Karlusich, J., Zinger, L., Loisel, H., Levy, M. and Bowler, C. Linking satellites to genes with machine learning to estimate phytoplankton community structure from space. **EGU Ocean Sci.**, 20, 217–239, <https://doi.org/10.5194/os-20-217-2024>, 2024